

OVERALL PROGRESS

Genetic evaluation and utilization

Rice germ plasm survey in Sambalpur, Orissa, India

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A program of the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, to collect rice germ plasm gives priority to upland and tribal areas of India where the gene erosion is relatively rapid. In Orissa, early types were surveyed and collected from Sambalpur and parts of two adjoining districts during kharif 1976.

Farmers in irrigated blocks of Attabira and Bargarh, with assured irrigation from Hirakud reservoir, grow only a few improved and high yielding varieties. T. 141 and Akulu, two improved local indicas, occupied about 70% of the rice area. Among the high yielding varieties, the gall midge-resistant Shakti (CR.93-4-2) in the medium lands and Jagannath in low lands were more popular. In the irrigated Dungeripalli block of the adjoining

Bolangir district, improved varieties also occupied a major rice area. T.141 and T.192 (locally called 192) were most popular. Farmers of the irrigated zones prefer to grow only a few improved varieties in kharif; in rabi, they grow mostly high yielding varieties.

In nonirrigated tracts, the genetic diversity was considerable. In Jharsuguda and Rairakhol subdivisions of Sambalpur district and in the adjoining parts of Dhenkanal, most farmers grow a number of local varieties, mostly early maturing. Fifteen to 20 varieties could be collected from any single village. The early varieties Guda Saria, Hari Sankar, Jhilli, and Kalakartika in the Jharsuguda tract, and Punei in the Rairakhol tract, were most common in uplands. During kharif 1976, 70 varieties from Sambalpur and about 800 varieties from all parts of India were added to the genetic stocks of the Institute. ❧

the last 4 years the screening was repeated under field conditions with high disease pressure. Two cultivars have given resistant reactions consistently. They have been named UPRB 30 and UPRB 31. During kharif 1976 their reactions were confirmed by pinprick and clip inoculation methods. Both cultivars are tall (130 cm); high tillering (15 tillers); with pigmented basal leaf sheaths and apiculi; long, narrow leaves; and medium-bold grains. Both mature in 130 days. UPRB 30 is awned; UPRB 31 is awnless. UPRB 31 is also resistant to blast disease. Studies of the allelic relationship of these new sources with the reported ones are in progress. UPRB 30 and UPRB 31 are being utilized in our breeding program. ❧

Reaction of certain rice varieties to stem rot diseases

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A field trial was conducted in 1975 kuruvai (June–October) to investigate the reaction of certain varieties to stem rot of rice incited by *Sclerotium oryzae* Catt. The natural occurrence of the disease was assessed during the grain maturity stage of the crop. The grain yield for the varieties was recorded. Of the 32 cultivars tested, 13 were relatively resistant compared with Jayanthi, which is representative of the susceptible group (see table). ❧

Varietal reaction of certain rices to stem rot disease. India, 1975.

Cultivar	Disease incidence (%)	Yield (t/ha)
IR71	0.5	3.3
CR-137-41-15	2.3	5.7
CR-137-41-2	2.4	5.6
CR-HP.3	3.1	4.7
IR272	3.9	5.2
Shiranui	4.9	4.5
RP-260-288-1-1	5.0	4.3
DCA-31	5.1	7.1
RP-1B-31	6.4	5.9
CR-137-36-30	6.8	8.1
CR-141-4004-1-191	7.9	2.0
Cult. 8946	8.2	4.7
Malagkit sunsong	8.4	1.3
Jayanthi	56.6	2.9

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Two possible new sources of resistance to bacterial leaf blight of rice

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All the released rice varieties that are resistant to bacterial leaf blight caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* derive their

resistances from a single source, TKM 6. In light of the reported variability in the virulence of *X. oryzae*, the use of diverse sources of resistance becomes obligatory.

At Pantnagar, India, in 1973, 93 distinct types were established from a boro rice collection (made in 1972) from previously unexplored areas of eastern Uttar Pradesh. They were screened for resistance to bacterial leaf blight. During

Reactions of boro varieties to bacterial leaf blight, Pantnagar, India, 1973–76.

Year	Varieties (no.)			Total
	Resistant (0-3)	Moderately resistant (5)	Susceptible (7-9)	
1973	1	7	84	92
1974	2	7	84	93
1975	3	11	79	93
1976	2	0	91	93